

APPENDIX F

Assessment criteria iteration 1

Table F.1

Assessment criteria by CPS Skill

CPS Skill	Assessment criteria
A1 Discovering perspectives and abilities of team members	Mention his/her ideas/opinions when necessary. Ask about the ideas/opinions of other group members.
B1 Building a shared representation and negotiating the meaning of the problem (common ground)	Mention what he/she understand of the problem to be solved. Ask about what others understand about the problem to be solved. Mention his/her ideas about the purpose of the problem Ask about others' ideas about the purpose of the problem.
C1 Communicating with team members about the actions to be/ being performed	Mention actions/plans to solve the problem. Ask about actions/plans of other group members to solve the problem. Mention what is necessary to solve the problem. Ask about what is necessary to solve the problem.
D1 Monitoring and repairing the shared understanding	Identify gaps (lack of information) in the understanding of the problem by his/her group. Identify errors in the understanding of the problem by the group. Mention ideas to resolve gaps (lack of information) in understanding the problem. Mention ideas to solve errors in understanding the problem.
A2 Discovering the type of collaborative interaction to solve the problem, along with goals	Ask about joint actions to be taken to solve the problem. Mention actions to be taken together to solve the problem.
B2 Identifying and describing tasks to be completed	Mention actions to be carried out by the other members of his/her group (control).
C2 Enacting plans	Mention the strategy (actions) to solve the problem.
D2 Monitoring results of actions and evaluating success in solving the problem	Evaluate the success of the strategy to solve the problem. He/She proposes changes in the actions to reach the solution.
A3 Understanding roles to solve problem	Ask his/her teammates about the roles they must take to solve the problem.
B3 Describe roles and team organization (communication protocol/rules of engagement)	Mention roles to be taken by him/her and his/her teammates.
C3 Following rules of engagement, (e.g., prompting other team members to perform their tasks.)	Mention actions to be carried out by the other members of his/her group (control) according to the assigned role.
D3 Monitoring, providing feedback and adapting the team organization and roles	Evaluate the success of the partners' actions to solve the problem. He/She proposes changes in the actions of his/her partners if the group can not reach a solution.